

PASS information

Title	Demonstration study 2.5.4 Sub-study 2 of the ConcePTION project. TeratoPHEN: Harnessing existing and newly developed systems to more rapidly identify and better delineate the full phenotype of known or suspected teratogens
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Active substance	UATC codes including, but not limited to N03 & L04
Medicinal product	See active substances
Product reference	Not applicable
Procedure number	Not applicable
Joint PASS	Not applicable
Research question and objectives	<p>Demonstration project 2.5.4 aims to investigate whether existing and newly developed pharmacovigilance and clinical genetics data collection systems can be harnessed to more rapidly identify and better delineate the full phenotype of known or suspected teratogens.</p> <p>This study, sub-study 2 (S2) will investigate reporting and recording of information relating to maternal medication use in pregnancy, genetic testing and offspring phenotype in a UK dataset held within Decipher, a global clinical genetics research database. It will also investigate what amendments to the Decipher database would be required to optimise the database for collection of pregnancy pharmacovigilance data with a focus on deep phenotyping of dysmorphology, congenital anomaly and follow-up of longer term outcomes.</p>
EFPIA partners	None
Academic partners /ENTIS centres	UZKN, UMAN, Decipher EMBL-EBI, DDD project (Wellcome Sanger Institute), NUTH
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2. List of abbreviations and definitions

2.1. List of abbreviations

- ATC - Anatomical Therapeutic Chemical classification system
- CAP – Complementary analysis project
- CDE - Core Data Elements
- Decipher - DatabasE of genomiC variation and Phenotype in Humans using Ensembl Resources
- DDD UK – Deciphering Developmental Disorders UK Study
- EFPIA - European Federation of Pharmaceutical Industries and Associations
- ENTIS- European Network of Teratology Information Services
- FACS - Fetal Anticonvulsant Syndrome
- HCP- Health Care Professional
- HPO - Human Phenotype Ontology
- IMI - Innovative Medicines Initiative
- MAH – Market Authorisation Holder
- NU – Newcastle University
- NUTH – Newcastle Upon Tyne NHS Foundation Trust
- PASS - Post Authorisation Safety Studies
- PV - Pharmacovigilance
- UMAN - University of Manchester
- UKTIS - UK Teratology Information Service
- UZKN - University of KwaZulu-Natal
- WP - Work Package

2.2. List of definitions

- Phenotype - the set of observable characteristics of an individual resulting from the interaction of its genotype with the environment.
- Deep phenotyping - precise and comprehensive analysis of observable traits that are a consequence or outcome of genetics, epigenetics, lifestyle, and environmental influences
- Genotype - the genetic constitution of an individual organism

3. Responsible parties

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This study is performed, in collaboration with Decipher (EMBL-EBI) colleagues and The Deciphering Developmental Disorders study (DDD) team (Wellcome Sanger Institute Website), as a pilot study under demonstration project 4 of task 2.5 in the IMI funded ConcePTION project

4. Abstract

4.1 Rationale and background:

Identification and characterisation of human teratogens has, to date, been slow and incomplete, particularly where documentation of neurodevelopment or longer-term health is concerned. The contributing factors are numerous, and include; suboptimal systems for data collection, a historical focus on major congenital anomaly rates as a proxy for assessment of fetal risk, incomplete and poor quality reporting of pregnancy exposures, lack of an immediately recognisable physical teratogenic phenotype, reporting of cases with undiagnosed genetic syndromes due to limited genetic testing available in the past, low numbers of pregnancy exposures and the lack of a co-ordinated approach to the identification and follow-up beyond infancy of exposed individuals.

4.2 Aim & Objectives:

Evaluate current reporting practices regarding maternal medication use in pregnancy, genetic testing and offspring phenotype within the Decipher database, a global clinical genetics research database. Identify opportunities for improving data collected by Decipher, with a particular focus on optimising capture of information on neurodevelopment and long-term health outcomes. Extend the Decipher fields and allow phenotypic data to be summarised by medication exposure type.

5. Amendments and updates

Number	Date	Section of study protocol	Amendment or update	Reason
1				
2				
3				

6. Milestones

	Milestone	Planned date
1.	Protocol approval	30/09/2025
2.	Submission to ConcePTION PMO of protocol for upload to Zenodo	20/10/2025
3.	Ethical and collaborator approvals in place for DDD-UK CAP	10/2024
4.	Start of DDD-UK data extraction	11/2024
5.	Start of DDD-UK data analysis *	20/03/2024
6.	Decipher Database modifications completed	12/2025
7.	Pilot data from exposure clinic reviewed	12/2025
8.	Data analysis (DDD) completed & internal report produced	12/2025
9.	DECIPHER ethics amendment to include teratogen exposure as primary indication for data capture	12/2025
10.	TeratoPHEN clinical / HCP collaborators recruitment initiated	01/2026
11.	Final report of 2.5.4 demo study submitted and peer review publication drafted	30/9/2025

*high level analysis only. Analysis of clinical information to commence following protocol publication

7. Rationale and background

7.1 Background

There is now a large body of literature demonstrating the detrimental impact of prenatal exposure to certain medications on fetal development. Through a process of astute clinician reporting, pre-clinical studies, and epidemiological studies in humans a considerable number of relatively common maternal medications have been shown induce alterations to fetal development that result in a combination of physical anomalies, growth alterations, and neurobehavioral impairments [1, 2]. However, very little is still known regarding the risk or safety of the majority of common medications for use during pregnancy. For those medications where concern has been raised, this is often on the basis of an observed association with major structural congenital anomalies, however, systematic examination and follow-up of the health and development of these individuals is typically lacking within pharmacovigilance systems.

This is important because a key principle of teratology is that, in order to be considered teratogenic, an exposure should be clearly shown to give rise to a characteristic pattern or phenotype of impairments. While there may be broad variation in the severity of the phenotypic expression of teratogenicity in exposed infants due to differences in genetic and environmental susceptibility, it is misleading to only focus on single major congenital anomalies when assessing the teratogenic potential of a specific medication [3].

Thus, understanding the wider physical and neurodevelopmental presentation is pertinent for the validation of the teratogenic capabilities of a particular medication. Further, it is only in delineating the wider pattern of impairment that one can understand the full impact of an exposure, and the extent of the care and long-term support (e.g. health care, social care, education etc.) that will be required for an individual who has been exposed to the medication. Current pregnancy pharmacovigilance systems do not adequately collect this level of individual patient phenotypic and genotypic detail, and do not provide a systematic approach to long term follow-up and documentation of the natural history of teratogenic syndromes. For this reason, the full impact of teratogenic effects frequently remain undocumented once pregnancy exposure is recognised

to be associated with structural anomalies in exposed offspring. As a consequence, delineation of the full phenotype of teratogens such as valproate has depended on the slow and fragmented collection of data through in-depth clinical assessments by small groups of geneticists and neuropsychologists with expertise in this area.

The diagnosis of a teratogenic syndrome therefore requires the exclusion of genetic disorders with overlapping features. For this reason, individuals with suspected teratogenic syndromes are frequently referred to clinical or medical geneticists for assessment and, where available and indicated, genetic testing. Fetal valproate syndrome, isotretinoin embryopathy and mycophenolate embryopathy are three teratogenic syndromes which have similar features to certain genetic disorders (i.e. they are 'phenocopies' of genetic syndromes).

This suboptimal approach has in turn hampered availability of this information, resulting in missed or delayed diagnosis of individuals with teratogenic syndromes. Access to, or integration into, pregnancy pharmacovigilance systems of clinical networks with expertise and infrastructure to support recording of detailed clinical features other than major malformations, along with genomic data offers an attractive option to improve the status quo.

If recognition and delineation of teratogenic syndromes is to be improved, it is key that the astute clinician method is utilised effectively in concert with structured follow-up studies to determine whether observed congenital anomalies are part of a phenotype that can be attributed to a teratogenic exposure, or whether they are an isolated symptom found by chance or as the result of another factor. The importance of this progression from astute clinician reports to in-depth study of exposed individuals is demonstrated by many of the teratogens described above. Isotretinoin, for example, was first identified as having a teratogenic effect in the mid-1980s following clear evidence of an increased incidence of major congenital anomalies [4]. However, it was not until years later when research began to explore the neurodevelopmental and functional outcomes of exposure to isotretinoin that the full extent of its teratogenic effects were uncovered. Not only was a wider pattern of effects demonstrated, there was also strong evidence that known structural anomalies did not account for the range of functional deficits

present in exposed children [5, 6]. Similarly, Valproate was initially identified by astute clinicians as precipitating a clear pattern of major congenital anomalies, but, following further detailed follow-up, has now also been shown to have a distinct and pronounced effect on a variety of neurodevelopmental outcomes [7].

Therefore, while the astute clinician method has been usefully exploited in the past, there is a need to develop it further by bringing it into the modern age and linking it more efficiently to further detailed follow-up studies in order to facilitate the delineation of full teratogenic phenotypes and reduce the unacceptable delays observed in many case (e.g. Valproate) between initial reports and regulatory or industry [8].

7.2 DECIPHER database

DECIPHER is a structured database used globally by clinical geneticists to share and compare phenotypic and genotypic data on patients with dysmorphic or malformation syndromes within or across multiple consortia. Currently, the DECIPHER database contains data from >50,000 patients who have given consent for broad data-sharing. DECIPHER also supports more limited sharing via consortia, including the DDD (Deciphering Developmental Disorders) Consortium in the UK which has recruited nearly 14,000 children with severe undiagnosed developmental disorders from around the UK and Ireland. These patients have undergone systematic examination and documentation of their clinical features, known as deep phenotyping, by their referring clinician who is required to capture the information in DECIPHER using the Human Phenotype Ontology coding system (<https://www.deciphergenomics.org/>).

Sharing of high quality clinical information via DECIPHER has greatly improved and accelerated the delineation of rare and previously unrecognised genetic syndromes. Optimisation of the Decipher database by adding key data fields for pregnancy pharmacovigilance (PV) to include documentation of longer term health and neurodevelopment would therefore be expected to improve:

1. Delineation of known or suspected teratogenic syndromes through more comprehensive and centrally co-ordinated data collection,

2. Reporting and identification of teratogenic syndromes by the global clinical Decipher network, essentially establishing a Virtual 'Astute Clinician' Platform, offering access to clinical expertise in deep phenotyping, genomic data interpretation and syndrome recognition,

3. Pharmacogenetic resources and capacity for better understanding the role of materno-fetal genetics and teratogenic risk.

7.3 ConcePTION project 2.5.4

The IMI-funded ConcePTION project aims to enhance the way the use of prescription medicines during pregnancy is studied ([ConcePTION 2018](#)). This is done in part by improving the collection, analysis and interpretation of pharmacovigilance data, to allow for a more systematic analyses and exchange of data. **WP2** (Work Package 2) focusses on sources of primary data collection.

Demonstration project **2.5.4** aims to develop novel investigatory systems which will allow researchers to delineate the full embryopathy/fetopathy phenotype for medications with proven or highly suspected teratogenic and/or fetotoxic effects. Although there can be considerable observational data available for such medications, the longitudinal endpoints of studies which have provided these data generally focus on malformation and other obstetric outcomes, generally described up to one year of infant age at most. As the longer-term developmental effects of *in utero* teratogenic/fetotoxic events are left undetermined, including any impacts medications may have on neurodevelopment and childhood health, safety assessments relating to the risk-benefit of medication use during pregnancy are often incomplete.

This study is sub-study 2 of the **2.5.4** demonstration project. A separate protocol has been published on the IMI ConcePTION website for sub study 1, which aims to explore the feasibility of collecting longer-term developmental outcome data from existing data sources including MAH enhanced pharmacovigilance databases.

8. Research question and objectives

8.1 Aim

To establish TeratoPHEN: A system to improve the detection, delineation and predicted risk of teratogenic syndromes through the systematic capture of detailed exposure, phenotypic and genotypic data through modification of the Decipher database and collaboration with established clinical networks.

8.2 Research Questions

Primary research question: Can the Decipher database be modified to support collection of detailed pregnancy pharmacovigilance (PV) data and pharmacogenetic studies of confirmed or suspected teratogenic agents?

The objectives are:

1. To analyse the historical reporting and recording for DDD patients in the Decipher database, as it currently stands, of data relevant to pregnancy PV.
2. To determine what amendments to the DECIPHER databases would be required to improve collection of detailed phenotypic, genotypic and long-term term outcome data for pregnancy pharmacovigilance.
3. To agree, and where feasible within budget and timescale of the project, implement amendments to these databases

9. Timelines

This demonstration project will run from April 2022 (month 37 of the IMI ConcePTION Study) until December 2025 (month 81, 9 months beyond the IMI ConcePTION Study official end as agreed by the ConcePTION MB).

Gantt chart

ConcePTION Month	37	-	66	67	68	69	70	71	72	73	74	75	76	77	78	79	80	81	
	20 22	-	2024					2025											
	A		S	O	N	D	J	F	M	A	M	J	J	A	S	O	N	D	
Ethics, Decipher CAP approval																			
Decipher database structure analysis																			
Analysis of DDD data																			
Pilot data from exposure clinic reviewed																			
Modification of Decipher database																			
DECIPHER ethics amendment																			
Establish international network & data capture																			
S2 Report																			

10. Research Design

10.1: Objective 1. To analyse the historical reporting and recording in the Decipher database as it currently stands, of data relevant to pregnancy PV.

Background & Rationale

The Decipher Database contains reported data from a wide range of projects, one of which is the DDD (Deciphering Developmental Disorders) Consortium in the UK which has recruited nearly 14,000 children with severe undiagnosed developmental disorders from around the UK and Ireland. Included in this cohort are children with undiagnosed congenital malformation syndromes which may or may not be associated with neurodevelopmental disorders, for whom history of exposure to medications *in-utero* is recorded, but not in a structured or systematic way.

Method

Analysis of anonymised data from the DDD project is permitted by collaborating centres and collaborators through submission to DDD of a Complementary Analysis Proposal (CAP) Form. DDD will, on approval of the submitted CAP proposal form, provide an extract of data within the DDD-UK dataset to the study members with authorised access. LY (UKZN, NUTH) and RB (UMAN) are members of DDD consortium and will lead on a CAP to analyse a data extract containing all DDD-UK cases with documented antenatal exposure to a medication(s) *in utero*. Descriptive analysis of this dataset will be undertaken to assess:

1. Reporting & recording of maternal antenatal medication use by UK geneticists (i.e. which exposures are recorded including comparison of anti-epileptic use versus other medications; documentation of key information such as timing of exposure, dose, indication etc)
2. To assess the extent of clinical features (phenotype) and genetic testing of individuals exposed to medications *in-utero*, the DDD-UK research dataset which was collected within the DECIPHER genetics database.
3. Reporting and recording of longer-term child health and development (i.e. what child developmental assessments or measures are recorded)

10.2.2: Objective 2. To determine what amendments to the DECIPHER databases would be required to improve collection of detailed phenotypic, genotypic and long-term term outcome data for pregnancy pharmacovigilance.

Background & Rationale

Building on the findings of objective 1 and through extended analysis of the DDD UK historical data extract, transformations and development required to extend the existing Decipher database to support the TeratoPHEN platform will be proposed.

Method:

1. Existing Decipher data fields will be mapped to the ConcePTION WP2 defined Core Data Elements (CDE) for primary pregnancy PV data collection to identify gaps in the existing data collection structure.
2. Existing HPO terms within the Decipher database will be reviewed against the WP2 CDE
3. Clinical data from the cohort of patients attending the NHS England commissioned Northern Fetal Exposure to Medicines Service (FEMS) pilot clinic will be reviewed in order to identify the most commonly used tests for assessing childhood development, and to identify whether clinical neurodevelopmental phenotypes can be adequately captured using the existing HPO terms within Decipher.

10.2.3: Objective 3. 1.To agree, and where feasible within budget and timescale of the project, implement amendments to these databases

Modifications to the Decipher database will be agreed in collaboration with Decipher colleagues (DP, JF, HF) based on cost and complexity of the modification as well as clinical importance and relevance. Updates required to optimize the system will be implemented throughout the course of the project, taking into account the Decipher budget and developmental capacity.

This newly developed Decipher 'TeratoPHEN' platform will be piloted and tested internally by the ConcePTION WP2 clinical team (lead by LY and RB) using data from local cases referred with suspected Fetal exposure syndromes, and then externally through collaboration with existing Decipher centres.

11. Data sources

DDD-UK study dataset which was collected using Decipher

Clinical cases referred with suspected Fetal exposure syndromes who have consented to data being entered on the Decipher database.

12. Quality control

Data will be reviewed by more than one researcher

13. Limitations of the research methods

Ascertainment bias

Databases / data collections cover different periods. Early collections not reflective of more recent methodologies.

Patients attending genetics clinic may be more likely to have a more severe or complex phenotype

Retrospective data collection, potentially many years post exposure. Recall bias, bias towards reporting of more severe adverse outcomes. May not be representative of full spectrum of outcomes

No denominator regarding total exposed population

Potentially small sample size if response to social media recruitment campaign or numbers of patients within genetics networks is small

Face to face clinical validation of phenotype / data reported may be required

14. Data management

DDD-UK data will be extracted, stored and analysed in accordance with the DDD data management protocols. A CAP has been submitted and approved by DDD-UK (March 2023, updated 27 March 2025 to include clinical information).

<https://www.deciphergenomics.org/ddd/complementary-analyses> (accessible to DDD project members only)

<https://www.sanger.ac.uk/about/who-we-are/research-policies/open-access-science/>

The DDD Study Collaborator Data Access Agreement can be openly accessed at:

<https://www.deciphergenomics.org/about/downloads/documents>

15. Funding

This study is funded by the Innovative Medicines Initiative: ConcePTION

16. Protection of human subjects

Collaborators providing data to TeratoPHEN will be required to follow relevant database, local and country specific regulations or policies.

Regional ethical committee (REC) approval has been sought (IRAS 111590/ REC 04/MRE05/50) to cover this project and the linked ConcePTION Demonstration study 2.5.3 (FES Study) jointly.

17. Management and reporting of adverse events/adverse reactions

Patients and health professionals providing data to the TeratoPHEN system will be made aware of the need to report adverse events according to nationally established processes.

18. Plans for disseminating and communicating study results

A report on TeratoPHEN will be submitted for publication in peer-reviewed journals. In addition, abstracts will be submitted for presentation at genetics, teratology, regulatory and pharmacovigilance conferences to raise awareness of and participation in the initiative, and promoted through EFPIA partners to encourage use of the system once established. Webinars, virtual stakeholder workshops/ engagement events will be held, and updates and study findings shared via social media.

19. References

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